

susceptibility in 1988 at RARS, Jagtial, and surrounding villages.

High GM incidence was observed in multilocation varietal trials during 1992 WS in Siam 29 derivatives Phalguna, Surekha, WGL 3962, and WGL 3943. Eswarakora derivatives were resistant (Table 2).

Phalguna, Surekha, and ARC5984, differentials derived from Siam 29 and belonging to group II, were susceptible to the local GM population in Karimnagar District in 1992-93, indicating a change in the pattern of reaction from biotype 1 to one similar to that of biotype 3. ■

Field screening of rice cultivars for resistance to gall midge *Orseolia oryzae* in coastal Karnataka, India

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Gall midge (GM) is increasing in incidence in the coastal region of Dakshina Kannada, Karnataka State. We screened 50 promising cultures for resistance during 1992-93 wet seasons (WS).

Cultures were transplanted in 4-m rows spaced at 20 cm. We recorded the number of tillers and percentage showing silvershoots 50 d after transplanting for 10 randomly selected hills per row. Ten entries were resistant (see table). ■

Reaction of promising rice cultivars to GM infestation in the field, Karnataka, India, 1992-93 WS.

Av silvershoots (%)	Lines
0-5	IET9691, IET11475, IET12179, IET12351, IET12797, IET12811, IR36, Abhaya, Suraksha, Shakthi
5-10	IET9683, IET10851, IET10318, IET11151, IET11375, IET11467, IET12186, IET12187, IET12188, IET12191, IET12419, H4, Sasyasree, Kasturi, Pusa Basmati 1, Jaldi 2, Jaldi 3
10-20	IET9553, IET10265, IET10720, IET11466, IET12183, IET12190, Jaldi 1, Jaldi 4, PNR162, PNR166, PNR519, PNR546, PNR381, IR22 (R), Ratna, Vibhava, Vikas, Mangala, Rasi
20 or more	Sonasali, Avinash, IR20, Jaya (check)

Stress tolerance

Response of rice plants from different regions to ultraviolet-B radiation

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Increased ultraviolet-B (UV-B) radiation (280-320 nm), as a result of stratospheric ozone depletion, has damaging effects on several plant physiological processes including photosynthesis, carbohydrate status, ion uptake, and ultimately, dry matter production. Species and varietal differences, in terms of sensitivity to enhanced UV-B, have been reported. Varietal differences have been noted in rice. It is possible that land races and cultivars originating from high UV-B areas have greater tolerance.

We tested the hypothesis that rice cultivars originating from regions with higher ambient UV-B radiation are more tolerant of UV-B radiation by evaluating their growth response to elevated UV-B radiation.

We screened 188 rice cultivars from various varietal groups and ecosystems, supplied by the International Rice

Number of rice cultivars in a group showing a significant reduction ($P < 0.05$) in plant height, tiller number, leaf area, and dry weight when exposed to 3 wk of enhanced UV-B radiation.

Group	Number of cultivars	Plant height	Tiller number	Leaf area	Dry weight
Indica	117	87 (74) ^a	26 (22)	39 (33)	40 (34)
Japonica ^b	55	42 (76)	8 (15)	15 (27)	13 (24)
Javanica ^b	7	5 (71)	5 (71)	3 (43)	3 (43)
Hybrid	9	9 (100)	2 (25)	5 (73)	5 (73)
Total	188	143 (76)	41 (22)	62 (28)	61 (32)

^aValues in parentheses represent the percentage of cultivars affected. ^bJaponica and javanica groups do not differ by isozyme analysis.

Germplasm Center at IRRI, for their growth response to UV-B treatment from 1991 to 1992. Cultivars were screened in batches of 22. Seeds were pregerminated at 30 °C for 24 h and then sown in 1-liter plastic pots containing 1.7 kg of Maahas clay soil fertilized with 0.4 g N, 0.04 g P, and 0.25 g K/kg soil.

Plants were grown in the greenhouse for 10 d and then subjected to UV-B treatment for 3 wk in a temperature- and humidity-controlled glasshouse (day/night temperature = 27/21 °C; relative humidity = 70%). UV-emitting fluorescent lamps supplied the UV-B radiation. Plants were irradiated for 6 h/d

(0900-1500 h). The average biologically effective UV-B radiation ($UV-B_{BE}$) was 13.0 kJ/m² per d. Six plants (2 pots) from each of the four replications were sampled after 3 wk of UV-B treatment. Plant height, tiller number, leaf area, leaf dry weight, and culm dry weight were determined. Plant dry weight was the sum of leaf and culm dry weight. The differences between the treated plant and corresponding control were analyzed using LSD test. The ambient UV-B radiation of origin was calculated based on latitude, longitude, and growing season according to the Björn and Murphy model.